

Dermatofibrosarcoma Protuberans Presenting as a Vascular Tumor in a Pediatric Patient

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ABSTRACT

Dermatofibrosarcoma Protuberans (DFSP) is a sarcoma with a prevalence of 1 per million prior to age 20 ^[1]. A five-year-old patient presented to the vascular anomalies clinic with the presumptive diagnosis of venolymphatic malformation. Despite concordant imaging studies, clinical history and exam challenged the diagnosis. Biopsy confirmed DFSP, successfully excised.

BACKGROUND

In 1924 Darier and Fernand first described Dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans (DFSP) but the definition of “DFSP” was not established until 1925 by Hoffman^[2]. DFSP is a monoclonal low to intermediate-grade soft tissue sarcoma of the dermal layer of the skin derived from mesenchymal cells. It is rare comprising 0.1% of all cancers and less than 2% of soft tissue sarcomas^[3].

The annual incidence, while rare, has increased to 4.2 cases per million of all tumors based on data from 9 cancer registries. It can present at any age but occurs most commonly between 20 and 50 years of age ^[3]. DFSP is even less common in children, however, some studies suggest DFSP often arises in childhood and its diagnosis is delayed until adulthood or may be misdiagnosed in childhood^[4]. While DFSP seems to be largely non-gender specific there is a slightly higher incidence in middle-aged females and elderly men ^[5]. DFSP is twice as likely in African Americans compared to Caucasians ^[6].

DFSP shows genetic and environmental associations. Studies illustrate that DFSP is caused by a chromosomal translocation at ^[7]. This results in COL1A1-PDGFB gene fusion ^[8]. There is an association between DFSP and adenosine deaminase-deficient severe combined immunodeficiency in children ^[9]. It is also often located at sites of past trauma including surgical scars, burns, radiation, insect bites, and vaccine and central venous line sites ^[10].

DFSP is most commonly found in the trunk comprising 42-72% of cases. The next most common locations are the proximal extremities (20-30% of cases) and the head and neck (10-16% of cases) [11].

Lesions present as mobile slow-growing skin-colored plaques with possible violet-red discoloration that are painless. The surrounding skin may also be telangiectatic [12]. Over time lesions can become protuberant or ulcerative [13]. On histology, DFSP is seen as monomorphic spindle cell proliferation in a storiform pattern in the dermis [14]. Depending on the time course of the lesion there may be a “grenz” tumor-free zone between the lesion and epidermis, melanin-containing dendritic cells (Bednar tumor), or a fibro sarcomatous component [15]. Immunostaining of DFSP is positive for CD34 and negative for factor XIIIa which can be used for diagnosis [16]. They are usually locally aggressive and tend to infiltrate adjacent structures, including subcutaneous tissue, muscles, tendons, and even bone structures leading to fixation with growth [17].

CASE PRESENTATION

A 5-year-old male presented to the vascular anomalies clinic for evaluation of a right flank mass. The patient had a history of a significant fall and trauma in the area more than a year before the presentation. They had been followed by a local pediatrician and a small amount of growth was noted over the course of a year. The patient had no other significant associations. The lesion was noted to be “dime-sized” and had a bluish discoloration of the skin. The initial diagnosis was an arteriovenous malformation due to the discoloration and an ultrasound was obtained.

Ultrasound imaging was inconclusive. The report included a heterogenous lesion with associated vascularity but most consistent with a venolymphatic malformation and a referral to the vascular anomalies clinic was made. Upon presentation, the patient was noted to have a 1.5 cm firm, but not hard, mass on the right flank, just superior to the iliac crest. The lesion had a 1 cm surrounding halo of pale skin. The lesion was freely mobile and not tender to deep palpation. There was a blue discoloration to the skin. No telangiectasias or hairy overgrowth was noted. No evidence of previous traumatic disruption of the skin was noted [Figure 1]. Physical examination was not consistent with a vascular tumor despite the ultrasound images and therefore MRI was obtained [Figure 2]. The MRI read was consistent with an indeterminate enhancing lesion favored to represent a low-flow vascular malformation such as venous or venolymphatic malformation. Cutaneous neoplasm is felt less likely.

Figure 1: Initial Presentation to the Vascular Anomalies Clinic.

Figure 2: Left T1, Fat-saturated MRI; Right, T2 weighted MRI

Given the inconsistencies between the clinical exam, the history, and the imaging reports, the patient was presented as part of the multidisciplinary vascular anomalies team. MRI over-read was still inconsistent with a definitive cutaneous neoplasm and biopsy was recommended. The patient's family was offered core-needle biopsy vs excisional biopsy with margins and elected for excisional biopsy. Excisional biopsy demonstrated DFSP with clear margins, but only 0.5 mm of clearance. **[Figure 3]** Repeat excision with 2 cm borders, down to the fascia was obtained and no residual tumor was identified. The patient healed without incident **[Figure 4]**. The patient is on every 6-month clinical follow-up for five years. No additional adjuvant therapies were warranted.

Figure 3: Pathology slides from excisional biopsy

Figure 4: 6 month post operative view of the excision site.

DISCUSSION

The only way to confirm a diagnosis of DFSP is by histological exam of a biopsy or post-excision of the tumor. Several imaging findings can increase suspicion of DFSP or aid in the treatment plan. Initial differential includes lipoma, hemangioma, epidermal cysts, keloid, dermatofibroma, nodular fasciitis, pyogenic granuloma, and Kaposi sarcoma depending on the stage of the mass [13]. Misidentification of DFSP as a benign lesion can lead to an increased risk of metastasis or invasion into surrounding structures. On Doppler sonography, DFSP can be considered by the presence of an oval mass in the subcutaneous tissue with a lobulated irregular margin with mixed

echogenicity [18]. In this case, the ultrasound was read as a vascular tumor due to the mixed appearance of the lesion, and the patient was referred to the multidisciplinary vascular anomalies clinic. Additionally, MRI can be used to determine the depth and the overall appearance to decide margins for surgical removal [19]. In this case, the MRI over-read was concerning for a solid soft tissue mass for which biopsy was recommended. The patient's family was offered core-needle biopsy but elected for excisional biopsy.

Standard treatment for DFSP is excision by Mohs microscopic surgery with wide margins to reduce the risk of recurrence [20]. In toddlers and even adolescents, Mohs excision is significantly more difficult. A systematic review in 2020 by Wang et. al. found 58 reported cases over a 25-year period with DFSP being the most common indication [21]. Our institution does not offer this service for toddlers or young adolescents which was the indication for excision with margins. Due to the high levels of anxiety in these younger patients, general anesthesia is often required and the dermatologic services do not perform Mohs on sedated patients.

DFSP is also radio-responsive and radiation can be used as adjunctive therapy when wide margins cannot be achieved due to the risk of cosmetic or functional deficits [22]. Imatinib, a PDGFR alpha and beta tyrosine kinase inhibitor, has been used in adults with DFSP that is unresectable and locally advanced, recurrent, or metastatic [23-24].

DFSP rarely results in death however it does have a high rate of reoccurrence [4,6]. There is also a rare potential for distant metastasis in 5% of cases. Due to the high risk of recurrence, current guidelines recommend an extended follow-up period of at least 5 years [25].

REFERENCES

1. Buteau AH, Keeling BH, Diaz LZ, Larralade M, Luna P, et al. Dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans in pediatric patients: A diagnostic and management challenge. JAAD Case Rep. 2018;4(2):155-158.
2. Darier J, Ferrad M. Dermatofibromes progressifs et recidivants ou fibrosarcomes de la peau. Ann Dermatol Syphiligr. 1924;5:545-562.
3. Stamatakis M, Fyllos A, Siafogianni A, Ntzeros K, Tasiopoulou G. Dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans: a rare entity and review of the literature. Journal of B.U.ON. : official journal of the Balkan Union of Oncology. 2014;19(1):34-41.
4. Reddy C, Hayward P, Thompson P, Kan A. Dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans in children. Journal of plastic, reconstructive & aesthetic surgery : JPRAS, 2019;62(6):819-823.
5. Hao X, Billings SD, Wu F, Stultz TW, Procop GW, et al. Dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans: update on the diagnosis and treatment. J Clin Med. 2020;9(6).

6. Criscione VD, Weinstock MA. Descriptive epidemiology of dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans in the United States, 1973 to 2002. Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology. 2007;56(6):968–973.
7. Stivala A, Lombardo GA, Pompili G, Tarico MS, Fraggetta F. Dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans: Our experience of 59 cases. Oncology letters. 2012;4(5):1047–1055.
8. Li N, Zhou T, Chen S, Yang R, Zhu Q. COL1A1-PDGFB gene fusion in dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans: a useful diagnostic tool and clinicopathological analysis. International journal of clinical and experimental pathology. 2018;11(8):4052–4059.
9. Fletcher CDM, Bridge JA, Hogendoorn P, Mertens F (Eds) WHO Classification of Tumors of Soft tissue and Bone. IARC, Lyon. 2013:77–79
10. Sanmartín O, Llombart B, López-Guerrero JA, Serra C, Requena C. [Dermatofibrosarcoma Protuberans] Actas Dermosifiliogr. 2007;98:77–87.
11. Stivala A, Lombardo GA, Pompili G, Tarico MS, Fraggetta F. Dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans: Our experience of 59 cases. Oncol Lett.
12. Lindner NJ, Scarborough MT, Powell GJ, Spanier S, Enneking WF. Revision surgery in dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans of the trunk and extremities. Eur J Surg Oncol. 1999;25:392–397.
13. Paramythiotis D, Stavrou G, Panagiotou D, Petrakis G, Michalopoulos A. Dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans: a case report and review of the literature. Hippokratia, 2016;20(1):80–83.
14. Sheidaei S, Salehi M, Abedian Kenari F, Jafari HR. Dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans challenges: a case series and review of the literature. Journal of medical case reports. 2023;17(1):18.
15. Mendenhall WM, Zlotecki RA, Scarborough MT. Dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans. Cancer, 2004;101(11):2503–2508.
16. Bhambri S, Desai A, Del Rosso JQ, Mobini N. Dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans: a case report and review of the literature. The Journal of clinical and aesthetic dermatology. 2008;1(1):34–36.
17. Eguzo K, Camazine B, Milner D. Giant dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans of the face and scalp: a case report. International journal of dermatology. 2014;53(6):767–772.
18. Shin YR, Kim JY, Sung MS, Jung JH. Sonographic findings of dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans with pathologic correlation. Journal of ultrasound in medicine : official journal of the American Institute of Ultrasound in Medicine. 2008;27(2):269–274.

19. Torreggiani WC, Al-Ismaïl K, Munk PL, Nicolaou S, O'Connell JX. Dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans: MR imaging features. AJR. American journal of roentgenology. 2002;178(4):989–993.
20. Ratner D, Thomas CO, Johnson TM, Sondak VK, Hamilton TA et al.
21. Mohs micrographic surgery for the treatment of dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans. Results of a multiinstitutional series with an analysis of the extent of microscopic spread. Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology. 1997;37(4):600–613.
22. Wang S, Ezaldein H, Delost G, Tripathi R, Stamey C. Safety and Efficacy of Mohs Micrographic Surgery in Children and Adolescents: A Systematic Review. Dermatologic Surgery. 2020;46(7):880-884.
23. Ballo MT, Zagars GK, Pisters P, Pollack A. The role of radiation therapy in the management of dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans. International journal of radiation oncology, biology, physics. 1998;40(4):823–827.
24. Lemm D, Mügge LO, Mentzel T, Höffken K. Current treatment options in dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans. Journal of cancer research and clinical oncology. 2009;135(5):653–665.
25. McArthur G. Dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans: recent clinical progress. Annals of surgical oncology. 2007;14(10):2876–2886.
26. Snow SN, Gordon EM, Larson PO, Bagheri MM, Bentz ML et al. Dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans: a report on 29 patients treated by Mohs micrographic surgery with long-term follow-up and review of the literature. Cancer, 2004;101(1):28–38.